

METHODS OF GROWING GRAPHITE UNDER NORMAL CONDITIONS AND TEMPERATURE

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Abstract. *The given article presents a simple and efficient method for preparing grown graphite, in which intercalation and graphite growth are accomplished in just one step under ambient conditions, without the use of heating or any complex equipment. We show that grown graphite obtained by a single-step process at room temperature yields an increase of up to 225 times. Most importantly, the amount of concentrated H₂SO₄ acting as an intercalant can be significantly reduced compared to traditional methods, significantly reducing the amount of wastewater and mitigating the harmful effects on the environment caused by excessive use of H₂SO₄.*

Keywords: *graphite, intercalation, sulfuric acid, graphite growth, ammonium persulfate, benzoyl peroxide.*

Introduction. It is important to suggest that in recent decades, the expanded graphite (EG) has attracted much attention as a new type of functional carbon material due to its potential application in thermal insulation, fire-resistant composites and other fields. At present time the discovery of graphene has attracted great interest in EG, since it is promising as a precursor for mass production of graphene through additional exfoliation in organic solvents with ultrasonic treatment [1]. Generally, EG rapidly heats graphite intercalation compounds synthesized by chemical oxidation or electrochemical method of natural shell graphite (NSG) [2,3].

Literature review. Firstly, the preparation process is complicated, including intercalation, water washing, drying and heat expansion and other procedures. Secondly, washing not only requires large amounts of water, but also leads to the problem of wastewater discharge. Thirdly, the thermal expansion of graphite intercalation compounds (GIC) must be realized by high temperature or radiation treatment. This leads to large energy consumption. Finally, the excessive use of concentrated sulfuric acid as an intercalant in the traditional method may cause serious environmental pollution [4]. Therefore, it is of great importance to find a simpler, more energy-efficient and less polluting approach to prepare EG. Here, we present a new and convenient method for the mass production of EG.

Experimental Part. It is worth mentioning that EG can be obtained under ordinary conditions with only one-step preparation. As a traditional preparation method, a two-component system consisting of ammonium persulfate ((NH₄)₂S₂O₈) and concentrated H₂SO₄ was often used to prepare EG. Surprisingly, by greatly reducing the amount of concentrated H₂SO₄ used, EG added to the two-component system at room temperature can be converted into fine-pored (worm-like) EG after simple mixing. The resulting expanded graphite (EG) shows a volume expansion (VE) of up to 225 ml/g, which is comparable with EG obtained by high-temperature or radiation

treatment [5.6]. The scheme of one-stage production of RRG is shown in Fig. 1. First, a mixture of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ with concentrated H_2SO_4 (98%) in different mass ratios was stirred ultrasound for 5 min. Then, 1 g of natural graphite (NG) (purity 99%, made in China) was added to the resulting mixture and stirred for 30 seconds to obtain a mixture of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$, H_2SO_4 and NG at room temperature.

It is not a secret that after a period of storage at room temperature, the mixture was transformed into RWG with a structural growth pattern. The OG value was determined by measuring the volume of RWG prepared from 0.2000 g of PG [7.8]. Figure 1 shows the morphological evolution of PG as a function of the residence time. The prepared mixture consists of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ (5 g), concentrated H_2SO_4 (3 ml), and PG (1 g). After mixing PG with the two-component solutions and then keeping for only 15 minutes, we observed the expansion of some PG fragments. With increasing residence time, the PG fragments gradually increase in size and expand similarly to RWG. The result of the time observation shows that after 12 hours, all PG fragments are completely transformed into RWG (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. The process of preparing RRG is carried out by a single-stage method at room temperature with holding. Thus, it can be concluded that a significant contribution to the formation of RRG should be made with $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ (ammonium persulfate), $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4$ (benzoyl peroxide). This is interesting, but this reason requires further study. It is known that $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$, $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4$ are chemically unstable and easily decompose in acidic solutions, leading to symmetrical rupture of bonds and the release of oxygen. Thus, a two-component system consisting of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ and concentrated H_2SO_4 is used to prepare RRG. $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ plays the role of oxidation of the edge of graphite and allows intercalation of H_2SO_4 (charge between ion molecules) to penetrate into the graphite layers.

At the same time, excess parts of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ can be attracted to H_2SO_4 without increasing its appearance during intercalation. Due to its chemical instability, the intercalated persulfate can decompose and release oxygen. There is an immediate increase in pressure inside the graphite interlayers and, consequently, the expansion of the GIC, as schematically shown in Figure 2.

It is obvious that the more gas is released, the higher are the pressure and the greater the expansion of the GIC. Since persulfate is responsible for gas formation, which can be considered as the main factor affecting the expansion of GIC at room temperature, a larger addition of persulfate indicates more gas formation and, thus, leads to a more pronounced expansion (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Mechanistic scheme of one-step production of room-temperature grown graphite.

As mentioned above, the one-step expansion of GCG at room temperature is caused by the instantaneous increase of gas pressure inside the graphite layers. For achieving this goal, two important factors are needed: one is the evolved gas, which causes the instantaneous increase of gas pressure to expand the graphite layers; and the other is the external pressure from the environment around the GCG. If the amount of H_2SO_4 is low, H_2SO_4 can completely join the reaction, and the GCG is exposed to the air atmosphere, which can lead to expansion. When the amount of H_2SO_4 used is increased, there is excess H_2SO_4 left, which surrounds the GCG and exerts additional pressure on them. This prevents the obvious expansion of GCG. Therefore, if H_2SO_4 is larger, the OP value will be lower.

Conclusion. By summarizing it should be suggested the observation for the preparation of RRG in a simple, energy-efficient and environmentally friendly way, where the method is significantly different from the traditional methods of preparing RG, in this approach, the preparation of RRG is simply a process of mixing PG with sufficient $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$, $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4$ and a small amount of concentrated H_2SO_4 and then keeping it at room temperature, without the need for washing or high-temperature treatment and without any complex devices. Comparing the obtained OR value with the RG value obtained by traditional methods, this approach was found to be preferable to traditional methods in the mass production of RG due to its simplicity, low cost and less pollution.

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